

V. Uluslararası Uygulamalı İstatistik Kongresi (UYİK - 2024)
İstanbul / Türkiye, 21-23 Mayıs 2024

UYİK

PROCEEDINGS

BOOK

**21- 23 MAY 2024
İSTANBUL- TÜRKİYE**

Using statistical methods and artificial intelligence for chronological attribution in Archeology
Oscar Trull¹, Joaquín Jiménez-Puerto², Blanca Pérez-Aguilar³, Francisca Sempere-Ferre¹

¹ Universitat Politècnica de València, Department of Applied Statistics, Operational Research and Quality, E-46022, Valencia, Spain

² Universitat de València, Department of Archeology, Postal Code, Valencia, Spain

³ Universitat Politècnica de València, E-46022, Valencia, Spain

*Corresponding author e-mail: otrull@eio.upv.es

Abstract

The arrangement of the finds and the diversity of their locations poses a problem for the chronological attribution of superficial archaeological collections. This is a process of great uncertainty and difficulty. The need for indirect dating makes its attribution even more complicated.

The use of statistical methods and artificial intelligence in this field is relatively new, but has great potential. The use of Machine Learning is allowing us to overcome barriers that traditional models cannot resolve.

In this article we present the process carried out to determine the chronological attribution to various archaeological packages of the Valencian Community. To achieve this, classification techniques have been tested; from a set of archaeological levels with well-known chronologies, which contain arrowheads, it has been possible to determine the dating of other sets of initially indeterminate chronology.

Keywords: *archeology, statistics, machine learning*

INTRODUCTION

Archaeological materials are generally classified typologically. The difficulty in establishing relationships or understanding their possible cultural or chronological meaning is very high, with those cases in which there is no associated C14 dating being especially sensitive. In these cases – which represent almost 80% of the data to be treated in this work – it is of great interest to have a scientific method that allows these archaeological collections to be associated with a specific chronological period. Therefore, in order to establish a methodology, statistical proposals based on the experience of other sources have been used in recent years, and which can be related to the archaeological objects to be dated.

Within the working group, bayesian tools have already been used that offer great results (Armero et al., 2020; Pardo-Gordó et al., 2022), although they are not free of problems, often derived from the nature of the data itself.

In this work, an approach is made to the use of techniques from Machine Learning, for chronological attribution of archaeological contexts lacking radiocarbon determination, using artificial intelligence (AI), exploring its classifying and predictive potential. AI-based methods are used for a multitude of tasks, although their use in the archaeological discipline is still incipient and is far from representing a homogeneous corpus. Usually they are focused on analysing images for classifications (Aprile et al., 2014; Caspari & Crespo, 2019). We apply artificial neural networks (ANN) to date archaeological undated objects. Other methods are also applied to test results.

The set to process consists of typological data of bifacial lithic arrowheads associated with the 3rd and 4th

millennium cal BC. These arrowheads are characterized in 7 groups depending on the shape.

The article is organized as follows: A section regarding materials and methods will analyse the methodology; results are shown in the results section, and finally, the discussion and conclusion in the last section.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material

The data set included in this article consists of the chronology of the archaeological levels of an a priori set covering radiodeterminations from 4600 to 3500 BP (uncalibrated). Data reflects counts of arrowheads located on the locations.

This set consists of only 55 units and has been used to generate the artificial intelligence models. Of this set, a subset was used to train the methods, while another subset (15%) was used for validation and testing. The target was to date a total of 280 objects undated.

Methods

The Collection of the Data

The first phase consists of the collection of archaeological information, mainly from bibliographic funds, from sites located in the Júcar and Segura hydrographic basins, for subsequent typological classification (See Figure 1). Many come from archaeological excavations, but a large number come from clandestine searches or from unclear contexts chronologically speaking.

Figure 1. Processes for obtaining chronological attribution.

The second phase consists of determining the age of those archaeological levels from which short-lived radiocarbon dating can be extracted. This set of dates is obtained in various locations and different strata, with a great variety of possibilities (mainly seeds or bones). This set is what will serve as the basis for the generation of the models, and has been called a priori set. For this task, the joint work between the statesman and the archaeologist is very important. The statistician must provide a mathematical view of the data obtained, while the archaeologist provides his experience and is the one who, when faced with an inference, will determine the dating of a set.

The dating process has consisted of classifying the archaeological objects (arrowheads of 7 types) into 5 specific phases. These phases have been agreed upon by the archeology team of the Universitat de València, and have been validated by another group of archaeologists. If any object is unclassifiable, it has been removed from the a priori dataset. The count of components of the a priori dataset is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Count number of arrowheads of types 1 to 7, assigned to a date phase.

	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4	Phase 5
Type 1	7	6	7	2	0
Type 2	11	6	1	0	0

Type 3	13	4	11	2	0
Type 4	4	2	13	6	0
Type 5	0	0	23	4	0
Type 6	1	0	0	0	0
Type 7	0	0	14	38	3

From these data, a statistical analysis has been carried out on the data to assign the dates to a subsequent set of validation data. Finally, a dating has been assigned to the objective set of undated archaeological objects.

Statistical Analysis

To carry out the analysis, classification methods based on machine learning included in MATLAB through the Classification Learner have been used. The Classification Learner tool facilitates the application of diverse classification methods. Decision Trees (Quinlan, 1986) utilize hierarchical structures to partition data based on feature values. Support Vector Machines (SVM) construct hyperplanes to separate classes in high-dimensional space (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995). k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) classify data points based on proximity metrics to their nearest neighbors (Cover & Hart, 1967). Ensemble methods like Random Forests (Breiman, 2001) and AdaBoost (Friedman, 2001) combine multiple classifiers to enhance predictive performance. These methods have been extensively studied and applied across diverse domains, with research validating their effectiveness in numerous studies. Classification Learner empowers users to efficiently leverage these algorithms for various classification tasks.

However, the main analysis was carried out using neural networks (NN) whose results were compared with the models listed above. The analysis carried out consisted of the use of a shallow neural network. Neural networks allow complex classification and regression problems to be solved, based on training and selection of hyperparameters (which define the structure of the neural network). Figure 2 shows the type of neural network used in this work, a shallow neural network.

Figure 2. Shallow neural network. The neurons are organized in layers and interconnected through weights.

Equation (2) encapsulates the mathematical framework of the neural network model, depicting how predictions $\hat{y}_{t+1}$ are derived based on a series of input variables x_t and bias b .

$$\hat{y}_{t+1} = f[x_t, x_{t-1}, \dots, x_1] + b \tag{2}$$

The neural network operates by connecting neurons according to specific axioms, with each connection characterized by weights w_i determined during the training process. These connections are integrated using an activation function $f(\cdot)$ along with an aggregation function $\Sigma(\cdot)$.

The training of the NN is carried out using the Mean Square Error (MSE) as a metric to determine the error made. And to select the hyperparameters of the network, and compare between them, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was used.

The network used consists of 7 variables and 3 hidden layers, of size 38, 12 and 233 whose activation function was used is $\tanh(\cdot)$.

RESULTS

The network was validated with a set reserved specifically for this purpose, and thus, predictions were made for the undated archaeological packages and for which no C14 dating is available. The distribution of allocations is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of the assigned chronological phases by the NN method.

The distribution obtained is expected, since the central phase predominates in the findings found. This is a phase that is also in transition from the oldest to the most modern. To contrast the results obtained, predictions were made using other machine learning methods, and the results were analyzed comparatively with those proposed with the NN. Table 2 shows the summary of these results.

Table 2. Comparison of dating proposals made with machine learning methods.

	Same prediction		Coincidences
All methods	30%	Tree	32%
At least 3	34%	SVM	36%
At least 2	0%	Boost	32%
None	36%		

It can be seen that in 30% of cases all prediction methods obtained the same result, and in 34% at least three methods coincided with the prediction. Of the methods used, the one that most often produced predictions similar to those proposed by the NN were the SVMs.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The use of artificial intelligence to make chronological attributions of archaeological levels lacking it allows us to incorporate a large number of elements into subsequent analyzes from a few measurements made with radiocarbon methods. In this article we have used regression and classification methods to date a set of almost 300 units from a small one of just 50. In the future it is intended to continue refining the method, which is in an initial phase, which would allow the samples used in archaeological analyzes to be substantially expanded, thanks to the incorporation of contexts from excavations lacking reliable dating.

The results show that this methodology can have a strong impact on the way new elements are attributed chronologically. These conclusions are only effective for this given assemblage, but in the future they can be extended to larger assemblages and to other elements of archaeological material culture such as ceramics or metal artifacts.

References

- Aprile, A., Castellano, G., & Eramo, G. 2014. Combining image analysis and modular neural networks for classification of mineral inclusions and pores in archaeological potsherds. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 50, 262–272. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2014.07.017>
- Armero, C., García-Donato, G., Jimenez-Puerto, J., Pardo-Gordó, S., & Bernabeu, J. 2020. Bayesian classification for dating archaeological sites via projectile points. *SORT*, 45(1), 33–46.
- Breiman, L. 2001. Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45, 5–32.
- Caspari, G., & Crespo, P. 2019. Convolutional neural networks for archaeological site detection – Finding “princely” tombs. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 110, 104998. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2019.104998>
- Cortes, C., & Vapnik, V. 1995. Support-vector networks. *Machine Learning*, 20, 273–297.
- Cover, T., & Hart, P. 1967. Nearest neighbor pattern classification. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 13(1), 21–27.
- Friedman, J. H. 2001. Greedy function approximation: a gradient boosting machine. *Annals of Statistics*, 1189–1232.
- Pardo-Gordó, S., Aubán, J. B., Jiménez-Puerto, J., Armero, C., & García-Donato, G. 2022. The chronology of archaeological assemblages based on an automatic Bayesian procedure: Eastern Iberia as study case. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 139, 105555. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2022.105555>
- Quinlan, J. R. 1986. Induction of decision trees. *Machine Learning*, 1, 81–106.

Acknowledgment

The authors thank the Department of Education, Culture and Sports of the Generalitat de València for funding the NeoNetS project “A Social Network Approach to Understanding the Evolutionary Dynamics of Neolithic Societies (C. 7600-4000 cal. BP)” (Prometeo/ 2021/007).

Conflict of Interest

The authors have declared that there is no conflict of interest.